

Legal Protection of Child Rights in Myanmar

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Abstract

In societies around the world, ensuring the survival of children is always given high priority. Children and youth are the future of any country. In Myanmar, children account for around 34 percent of the total population of over 55.8 million based on the census conducted in 2014, on 1 October, 2022. Children have the rights to be protected from harm, abuse, neglect, exploitation and violence. Children have the rights care and protected not only national Organizations but also UN Organizations. The government has the main responsibility to ensure the rights of children are protected and provided for. All citizens have responsibilities to respect the rights of the children as well. Although the best interests of the child are not yet defined, every decision must be made first and foremost when making decisions for the child.

Keywords: *Child Rights, Need of Care and Protection of Child.*

1. Introduction

Children's rights include the right to health, education, family life, play and recreation, an adequate standard of living and to be protected from abuse and harm. Children's rights cover their developmental and age-appropriate needs that change over time as a child grows up. These rights are listed in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. Almost every country has agreed to these rights. Children are our precious gems. Every child has the right that provides as the fundamental right under international conventions such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), International Labor Organization, ILO Convention No.182 on the Worst Forms of Child Labor, ILO Convention No. 138 on the Minimum Working Age and United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 2030. Furthermore, the Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2008, Sections 21, 32(a), 351, 366 and 390 enact the right to education for children, protection of the rights of children, striving for development of human resources and protection of the rights of workers. There are many specific laws and related laws deals with the legal protection of the child rights in Myanmar. In practice, the main issues are the weak of enforcement of laws, rules of law, poverty, lack of education and lack of jobs opportunity although it has been trying for protection of the child rights legally under existing laws. Everybody have the responsibilities to protect the rights of child throughout the world including Myanmar.

2. Aims and Objectives

The aims and objectives are as follows;

- to prevent of abuse, neglect, exploitation and violence against children,
- to protect of children who are experiencing hurt or discrimination,

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- to promote the best interests of children and the rights of the child according to the law,
- to reintegrate of children who have been expected to neglect or abuse back into their families and communities.

3. Definitions of Child

A juvenile is a child or young person who is not yet old enough to be regarded as an adult. Juvenile activity or behavior involves young people who are not yet adults. A juvenile or child means a person who has not completed eighteen years of age.² A Child means every human being below the age of eighteen years unless, under the law applicable to the Child, majority is attained earlier.³ The term child shall apply to all persons under the age of 18 years. Child means a person who has not attained the age of 18 years.⁴ Child means a person has not attained the age of 18 years.⁵ Child means a person has not attained the age of fifteen years.⁶

But it should be noted that if a boy above 18 years of age marries a girl under 14 years of age with or without the consent of her parents, he offends against the provision of the Child Marriage Restraint Act and exposes himself to punishment. “Early childhood” means that is from birth to age of eight years.⁷

In the Myanmar context, a juvenile or minor or child is any person who is below the age of 15 years. However, the Child Rights Law specifies that a child cannot be charged for any crime until he has attained ten years of age. Nothing is an offence which is done by a child above 10 years age and under 12, who has not attained sufficient maturity of understanding to judge of the nature and consequences of his conduct on the occasion.⁸

The child definition above mentioned generally analyses that a child means a person who has not completed 18 years of age. Today this is a universally accepted definition of a child which comes from the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC).

4. Types of Child Rights

There are four kinds of Child Rights: Survival Rights, Development Rights, Protection Rights and Participation Rights.

4.1 Survival Rights

Survival rights include the child’s right to life and the needs that are rest basic to existence, such as nutrition, shelter, an adequate living standard and access to medical services.

Rights that are necessary for the existence of the child: rights to parental guidance consistent with the child’s evolving capacities,⁹ rights to life, survival and development,¹⁰ the child has the right to be a name and nationality and the child has right to know and be cared

² www.collins-english-dictionary.com

³ Article 1 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

⁴ Section 3(m) of the Human Trafficking Prevention and Suppression Law, 2022.

⁵ Section 3(b) of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

⁶ Section 2(a) of Oil-Field (labor& Welfare) Act, 1951.

⁷ Section 2 of the Early Childhood Care and Development Law, 2014.

⁸ Section 78 (a), (b) of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

⁹ Article 5 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹⁰ Article 6 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

for his or her parents,¹¹ rights to live with his parents and not to be separated from them unless this is necessary for the best interest of the child,¹² rights to enter or leave a state party for the purpose of family reunification and to maintain relations,¹³ right to highest standard of healthy and medical care attainable,¹⁴ right to benefit from social security including social insurance,¹⁵ and right to adequate standard of living.¹⁶

Section 4 (c) of the Child Rights Law provides to put into practice the necessary arrangements including basic health, nutrition and access to educational opportunity for all-round development of children. The State recognizes that every child has the right to survival and development.¹⁷ Every child shall have the inherent right to survival and the right to stay together and grow up with one or both of his or her parents if they are still alive.¹⁸

Medical care, nutrition, protection from harmful habits (including drugs) and safe working environments are under the right to health. And access to special care and support for the special needs children.

4.2 Development Rights

Development rights include the right to education, play, leisure, cultural activities, and access to information, and freedom of thought, conscience and religion.

Rights that ensure that a child is given all opportunities to develop his/ her potential and evolve into a well-rounded individual: rights to life, survival and development,¹⁹ right of access to information and material from diverse sources and media,²⁰ right to development through parental responsibility,²¹ right to access standard healthcare and medical services,²² right to education with aims at developing the child's personality, talents, and mental and physical abilities to the fullest extent,²³ right of children of minority communities and indigenous populations to enjoy their own cultural and practice their own religion and language²⁴ and right to recreation and cultural activities.²⁵

A right to education is paramount in this regard as it helps children maintain discipline and enhance life skills while finding a safe and healthy environment to nurture physiological development. This environment can only be achieved with the inclusion of freedom from violence, abuse or neglect. Therefore, education is a very important part of the development.

¹¹ Article 7 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹² Article 9 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹³ Article 10 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹⁴ Article 24 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹⁵ Article 26 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹⁶ Article 27 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

¹⁷ Section 18 of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

¹⁸ Section 19(a) and 19(c) of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

¹⁹ Article 6 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²⁰ Article 17 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²¹ Article 18 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²² Article 24 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²³ Article 28 and 29 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²⁴ Article 30 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²⁵ Article 31 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

4.3 Protection Rights

Protection rights: ensure children are safeguarded against all forms of abuse, neglect and exploitation, including special care for refugee children, safeguards for children in the criminal justice system, protection for children in employment, protection and rehabilitation for children who have suffered exploitation or abuse of any kind.

Rights that guarantee that a child is safe from any dangerous influence or situations that may be prejudicial to the child: right to protection from all forms maltreatment, abuse and neglect,²⁶ State has an obligation to provide protection for children without family,²⁷ right to protection of refugee children and children with disability,²⁸ right to protection from child labor, drug abuse, sexual exploitation, sale, trafficking, abduction, torture, deprivation, arm conflicts or any other exploitation,²⁹ and right of children in conflict with the law to treatment which promotes his/ her dignity and worth.³⁰

4.4 Participation Rights

Participation rights: encompass children's freedom to express opinions, to have a say in matters affecting their own lives, to join associations and to assemble peacefully. As their capacities develop, children should have increasing opportunity to participate in the activities of society, in preparation for adulthood.

Rights that guarantees a child is heard and given a voice in any decision-making process that affect him/her: right to and for it to be taken into account in any proceeding affecting him/ her, express his/her opinion freely,³¹ right to freedom of expression, receive and impart information,³² right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion,³³ right to freedom of association and of peaceful assembly³⁴ and right to protection if privacy, family, home or correspondence.³⁵

The rights of the child have been given top priority in the global agenda. The Government of Myanmar is giving top priority to the children traditionally as well as legally. Since Myanmar's accession to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Government have laid down and implemented programs at the national level.

5. Protection of Child Rights

Some children could be forced into hard labor, face criminal charges as adults and were often married as adults. In Myanmar, every child has the rights care and protected not only national laws but also UN Organizations such as ILO, WHO, UNICEF, ASEAN and others organizations.

5.1 International Conventions relating to Protection of Child Rights

Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.³⁶ Parents have a

²⁶ Article 19 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²⁷ Article 20 and 21 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²⁸ Article 22 and 23 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

²⁹ Article 32 to 39 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³⁰ Article 40 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³¹ Article 12 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³² Article 13 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³³ Article 14 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³⁴ Article 15 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³⁵ Article 16 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989.

³⁶ Article 25(2) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948.

prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children.³⁷ Every child shall have, without any discrimination as to race, color, sex, language, religion, national or social origin, property or birth, the right to such measures of protection as are required by his status as a minor, on the part of his family, society and the State. Every child shall be registered immediately after birth and shall have a name. Every child shall have the right to acquire a nationality.³⁸

Special measures of protection and assistance should be taken on behalf of all children and young persons without any discrimination for reasons of parentage or other conditions. Children and young persons should be protected from economic and social exploitation. Their employment in work harmful to their morals or health or dangerous to life or likely to hamper their normal development should be punishable by law. States should also set age limits below which the paid employment of child labor should be prohibited and punishable by law.³⁹

Myanmar has ratified ILO Convention No. 182 on the worst forms of child labor in December 2013, ILO Convention No. 138 on the minimum working age in June 2020 and UN Convention on the Rights of the Child in July 1991. In Myanmar, child labor was mostly seen in agricultures, factories, tourisms, ICT companies, tea shops, beer stations and restaurants. Child labors are not accepted ILO Conventions 138 and 182 and to the UN Convention on the Rights of the child. The Convention “138” sets the general minimum age for work at 15 years and minimum age for hazardous work at 18 years.

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations on 20 November 1989. The CRC entered into force in 1990 and is now the most widely ratified human rights treaty in history. The CRC solves problems using the best interests of the child “ as a guiding principle”. The CRC is guided by four overarching principles set out in General Comment No. 12 (2009). They are intended to strengthen both the understanding of children’s rights, and to influence how children’s rights are protected by State and families.

Myanmar has ratified the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, which includes four core principles: non-discrimination; devotion to the best interests of the child; the right to life, survival and development; and respect for the view of the child.

Non-discrimination: children should not be denied their rights because of discrimination.⁴⁰ The best interests of the child: when making decisions about children, the best interests of the child should be the most important criteria.⁴¹ Survival and Development of the Child: the life and survival of the child should be of the utmost importance to States in their activities, and they are obligated to ensure children develop into healthy adults.⁴² Respect of the views of the child, or rights to participate: children should be able to participate in decisions that concern them according to their age and maturity.⁴³

Myanmar acceded to the Convention on 15th July 1991. With reservations on articles 15 and 37 and it became a State Party to the Convention on 14th August 1991. In order to

³⁷ Article 26(3) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948.

³⁸ Article 24 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1976.

³⁹ Article 10 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 1976.

⁴⁰ Article 2 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989

⁴¹ Article 3 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989

⁴² Article 6 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989

⁴³ Article 12 of the Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC), 1989

implement the rights of the child embodied in the CRC, the Child Law was promulgated on 14th July, 1993 and the reservations were also withdrawn on 19th October 1993.

Myanmar has ratified the Optional Protocol: Sale of Children, Child Prostitution, and Pornography. The protocol was adopted by the UN General Assembly on May, 2000 and entered into force on January 18, 2002. Myanmar also ratified the Optional protocol to the CRC on Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography on 17 January 2012.

Myanmar has ratified the so-called “child soldier treaty”, formally known as the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict (CRC-OPAC). The significance of this protocol is that it bars the states from using children under the age of 18 for military purpose; it also requires states to make sure all armed groups distinct from (state) armed forces ensure there is no military use of children under the age of 18. The protocol was adopted by the UN General Assembly on May, 2000 and entered into force on Feb 12, 2002. Myanmar is the 169th country to ratify the protocol. Myanmar also ratified the Optional Protocol to the CRC on the involvement of Children in Armed Conflict on 27 September 2019. The UN and the Myanmar Government signed a Joint Action Plan to end the recruitment and use of children in June 2012, and the Myanmar government signed the CRC-OPAC in 2015.

The military has discharged children from service in several releases. The Tatmadaw allowed 1,579 soldiers under the age of 18 to resign between 2014 to March 2019. Children suffer from grave violations related to armed conflict between the Tatmadaw and ethnic armed groups, particularly in Kachin, Shan and Kayin states. In accordance with the Action Plan, suspected minors should be identified and released immediately without conditions.

Myanmar ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child in 1991, and enacted the Child Law in 1993. However, the original law had no provisions regarding the military use of children. The Union Parliament passed amendments to the law in July 2019 introducing a new chapter on children and armed conflict. Sections 63 and 64 of the Child Rights Law bar the Tatmadaw and non-state armed groups from recruiting and conscripting children under the age of 18 years.⁴⁴

The United Nations Security Council Resolution No. 1612 (2005) and subsequent resolutions, the Six Grave Violations against children during the armed conflict, causing death and injury to children; recruiting minors into armed groups; attacks on schools and hospitals; committing sexual violence; to prevent the abduction of children and the blocking of humanitarian aid to children, the “Committee on the Prevention of Serious Abuses against Children in Armed Conflict”. It was formed on 7 January 2019.⁴⁵

As Myanmar is a member of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, in order to serve the best interests of children and enjoy children’s rights in accordance with the law, the Committee for the Prevention of Serious Offenses against Children during Armed Conflict has been established and implemented, especially in order to protect children during armed conflict.

In doing so, the National Action Plan (2020-2021) for the Prevention of Death and Injury to Children and Sexually Violent Crimes During Armed Conflict was implemented from (10-8-2020) to (10-8-2021), the safety of children who have suffered serious violations

⁴⁴ <https://burma.irrawaddy.com/news/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.ddm.gov.mm/?p=58682>

during armed conflict; A survival-centered approach is being applied, such as ensuring that personal information is not leaked and treated with respect. The “Country Task Force on Monitoring and Reporting – CTFMR” was signed on (27-6-2012) between the Government of the Republic of Myanmar and the United Nations Country Task Force on Monitoring and Reporting (CTFMR).⁴⁶

Everybody who violates the provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child will be effectively punished and action will be taken in accordance with the policy of zero acceptances of serious crimes against children during armed conflict.

5.2 Myanmar Legal Framework for Protection of the Child Rights

Protecting children from violence is one of the most important duties of both State and family. Every child has a right to protection from abuse, neglect, violence and exploitation. In Myanmar, every child is protected under many laws; such as Constitutional Law, the Penal Code, the Code of Criminal Procedure, Labor Laws, the Human Trafficking Prevention and Suppression Law, 2022, Educational Laws, especially is the Child Rights Law, 2019.

The Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar (2008), in Chapter VIII, Sections 345 to 390 is provided that citizen, fundamental rights and duties of the citizens. The Union shall guarantee any person to enjoy equal rights before the law and shall equally provide legal protection.⁴⁷ The Union shall not discriminate any citizen of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, based on race, birth, religion, official position, status, culture, sex and wealth.⁴⁸ Mothers, children and expectant women shall enjoy equal rights as prescribed by law.⁴⁹

In section 488 (1) of the Code of Criminal Procedure (1898), if any person having sufficient means neglects or refuses to maintain his legitimate or illegitimate child unable to maintain itself, the Court may order him to make a monthly allowance not exceeding K.50,000 in the whole.⁵⁰ (2016 Amendment Law).

The Penal Code is provided that the protection of child rights: causing miscarriage, causing death of quick inborn child by doing act likely to cause death or pregnant woman, exposure and abandonment of child under twelve years by parent or persons having care of it, concealment of birth by secret disposal of dead body, hurt and grievous hurt, kidnapping from lawful guardianship, selling and buying minor for purposes of prostitution, rape and unnatural offences.⁵¹

The Human Trafficking Prevention and Suppression Law, 2022 is provided that the Central Body and relevant Working Groups shall give and carry out special protection of trafficked victims, women children and youth; such as their dignity, identification, necessary security and assistance, send them back to their parents, other suitable and secure protection, freedom of expression of their desire and freedom of choice according to their age and maturity, special arrangement for remedy of their physical and mental damage, in a private office (in camera) where the public can't be heard, giving vocational education based upon

⁴⁶ <https://infosheet.org/mm/>

⁴⁷ Section 347 of the Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2008.

⁴⁸ Section 348 of the Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2008.

⁴⁹ Section 351 of the Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2008.

⁵⁰ Section 488(1) of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898 amended in 2016.

⁵¹ Section 312, 316, 317, 318, 319, 320, 361, 372, 373, 376 and 377 of the Penal Code, 1860.

education and technique and medical examination and medical treatment with their consent and give protection by keeping confidential the information relating to them. Whoever convicted of trafficking in women and children shall be punished to a minimum of ten years to a maximum of imprisonment for life and shall also be fine.⁵²

In National Education Law, 2014, every child has the rights to education are provided that related to early childhood care and development education from birth to age eight, preschool is age 3 to 5, kindergarten is 5 year old. Basic education that every citizen must learn, the Nation designates as “free and compulsory education”. A special education program was the establishment of schools which have special programs to teach disabled children.

Myanmar has finally enacted a new law to protect the rights of children in 23rd July 2019. This law is fully enacted to the rights of the child. It is included 30 Chapters and with 121 Sections. Therefore, for our next generation the new Child Rights Law was written, and is consistent with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and is to be adaptable to changing situations in the country. There must be rules within the new Child Rights Law to implement the rights of our children. Before the law, every child must have equal opportunities. Therefore, the rules which will be drafted soon must guarantee granting equal rights and benefits for every child in different areas.

Under the newly enacted Child Rights Law, a child is defined as anyone under the age of 18. Today, all children born in Myanmar are guaranteed to the fundamental and unconditional right to register at birth. Birth registration is the first right of the child and a stepping stone to enjoying other rights such as the right to health, education and protection. With the establishment of a minimum age of marriage (18 years) and to employment (14 years), the value of childhood is recognized and helps allow children be children. The new chapter on proper regulation of care arrangements puts importance for children’s welfare wherever they reside. Stability and certainty regarding who provides for a child’s basic needs is a necessity to make children feel safe. All forms of violence against children are prohibited. The law also recognizes that children affected by armed conflict need special protection by criminalizing grave violations against children and providing stronger legal protection for children in the context of armed conflict.⁵³

The Child Rights Law sets the minimum age of employment at 14 years and forbids children from doing dangerous forms of labor. Children laborers in Myanmar often work long hours. According to national laws, working hours for children are limited to four hours per day. In practice, young workers work the same as adults. However, there are few benefits and the risk of abuse. Nowadays, majority of child labor is facing work more than 50 hours per week. Children in Myanmar receive lower wages than adults. Furthermore, children who work for their families often do not receive compensation for their labor. Even when they do earn, it is often paid directly to the family, sometimes without ever passing through the children’s hands.

The State recognizes that every child has the right to survival, development, protection and care and to achieve active participation within the community. Every child has the inherent right to life and the parents or guardian shall register the birth of the child in

⁵² Section 35 of the Human Trafficking Prevention and Suppression Law, 2022.

⁵³ <https://www.unicef.org/myanmar/press-releases/enactment-new-child-rights-law-government-myanmar>

accordance with law. Every child shall have the right to citizenship, health, education, disabled child, in accordance with the provisions of the existing law.

The following child is a child in need of care and protection – one who has no parents or guardian; one who is in the custody of the cruel or abusive parents or guardian; one who is employed by worst form; one who is stayed on street; one who is faced a case in court; one who is sexually exploited; one who is trafficked; one who is divorced or separated parents; one who is suffering from AIDS disease or his parents is suffering from AIDS disease; one who earns his living by begging; one who is employed in production, selling and transportation a narcotic drug or a psychotropic substance; one who is of unsound mind or is afflicted with a contagious disease; one who is of so depraved a character that he is uncontrollable by his parents or guardian; one who is affected by natural disasters or armed conflicts; one who is poverty and disabled; and one who is prescribed by the Ministry from time to time.⁵⁴

On 2017, the Innwa Tailor Shop Case, it was mediated by Human Rights Commission; the victims agree to settle the case with fifty million kyats instead of pursuing the case in court. However, the Court sentenced the store's owner and the family under the Anti-Trafficking in Persons Law, the Child Law and Section 325 and 326 of the Penal Code. In another case, on December 28, the child who was over 4 years abused by his father and stepmother for stealing condensed milk and sugar at the Shwe Kyin Township, Bago Division. His father and stepmother who assaulted the child are about 25 years old, and the two have been arrested and punished with Section 103(a) of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

Every child shall abide by the ethics and discipline, according to his age, such as upholding and abiding by the law, obeying the advice and instruction of parents or guardian and teachers, abiding by the school discipline, work discipline and community discipline, cherishing and preserving the race, language, religion, culture, customs and traditions concerned with him, abstaining from taking alcohol, smoking, using narcotic drug or psychotropic substances, gambling and other acts which tend to affect the moral character.⁵⁵

Parents, teachers and guardians shall give guidance to ensure that the practice of abiding by the ethics and discipline, is infused into the children. The fundamental responsibility of the parents is designed to protect children from all forms of harm, abuse and neglect. The value of human society depends upon how it protects its children. The child protection requires everyone to take responsibility and that every child matters. Therefore, all children have the right to be protected from all types of harms.

6. Conclusion

Every child has the right to be safe and protected from all forms of harm, including, but not limited to, protections from physical, emotional, and sexual abuse as well as from neglect and negligence. Myanmar can achieve its wider national goals for growth and prosperity and fulfill targets for the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030. The government and relevant Ministries put into practice the necessary arrangements including basic health, nutrition and access to educational opportunity for all round development of children. The State, volunteers and non-government organizations provide the children who are the victims of neglect, abuse, cruelty and exploitation. They strive for the ethical

⁵⁴ Section 57 of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

⁵⁵ Section 68 of the Child Rights Law, 2019.

correction of juvenile offenders by proceeding the trial of juvenile crimes separately. Therefore, by implementing the rights of the child recognized in UNCRC, 1990 and the Child Rights of Law, 2019, the life of children will shine in the future.

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